

Development of a GIS Tool for Assessing Nitrate Contamination Risk in Groundwater: Gediz Basin Case Study

C. Aydoner^{1*}, I. Yolcubal², S. Aynur³, Y. Kurucu⁴, B. Esetlili⁴, T. Esetlili⁴, Y. Gurbuz⁵, O. Sezgin⁵, İ. Özenç⁵, P. Hışır⁵

¹TUBITAK MAM, Gebze, Kocaeli, cihangir.aydoner@tubitak.gov.tr

²Istanbul Technical University, Maslak, Istanbul, yolcubal@itu.edu.tr

³Formerly at TUBITAK MAM, current email: sebnem.aynur@gmail.com

⁴Ege University, Bornova, İzmir, yusuf.kurucu@ege.edu.tr, bihter.colak@ege.edu.tr, tolga.esetlili@ege.edu.tr

⁵Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry, yusuf.gurbuz@tarimorman.gov.tr

*Corresponding author

Abstract

The assessment of groundwater vulnerability to pollution is essential for identifying and protecting zones affected by nitrate contamination due to intensive agricultural activities. Groundwater quality monitoring requires sample collection and laboratory analysis, making it an expensive process. It is essential to make decisions for areas without water quality monitoring. A risk assessment method is proposed in this study which combines intrinsic vulnerability and presence of nitrogen pollution sources for determination of nitrate contamination risk in groundwater. Intrinsic vulnerability is defined as the ease with which contaminants reach groundwater, influenced by geological and hydrological factors. Nitrogen pollution sources include nitrogen loads into the analysis. The assessment method that has been developed, used risk matrices, giving risk of nitrate contamination of groundwater. A case study in the Gediz River Basin demonstrates the validity of such methods by comparing risk analysis results with monitoring data. This method can be used by regional authorities to identify nitrate pollution risks through the GIS tool developed.

Keywords

Groundwater; GIS tool; nitrate vulnerability; risk assessment.

INTRODUCTION

In 1991, the European Union introduced the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) to reduce and prevent water pollution from agricultural nitrates. This directive requires member states to establish monitoring systems, identify nitrate vulnerable zones, and implement protection plans.

According to Article 3 of the Directive, all areas contributing to water pollution must be classified as vulnerable. While the EC recommended declaring nearly the entire basin vulnerable. Considering that this classification can pose significant challenges for agriculture and livestock farming, studies have been conducted in Italy to limit the areas defined as vulnerable from a pollution risk perspective (*De Maio et al., 2007*). This study proposes a method for assessing groundwater vulnerability to nitrate pollution with combining intrinsic vulnerability and presence of pollution sources at micro-watershed level. (*Aydoner, 2024*). The proposed method provides making decisions for areas without water quality monitoring as well (*Baalousha, 2010*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This paper presents a methodology for assessing nitrate pollution vulnerability at basin scale. The approach combines groundwater contamination vulnerability with the presence of nitrogen pollution. At the basin scale, groundwater intrinsic vulnerability was assessed from a hydrogeological perspective, using data on the basin's geology, groundwater depth, soil texture, precipitation, and topography. Nitrogen pollution is evaluated using matrices that analyze various agricultural pollution sources by estimating nitrogen loads generated from agricultural activities. By integrating these two

methods, the proposed approach estimates the risk of nitrate contamination in groundwater, providing a practical tool for regional-scale risk assessment. Both the **groundwater contamination vulnerability index** and the **nitrogen pollution index** were calculated using a GIS-based tool developed in this study. This tool enables the rapid and accurate determination of risk of nitrate contamination, enhancing the efficiency and precision of the assessment process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The risk method overlays and combines data and maps of various factors that influence intrinsic vulnerability and nitrogen pollution load resulting in a risk level from insignificant to very high as depicted in Figure 1. The risk analysis results are compared with the long term average groundwater nitrate concentrations with classes determined by the EU Commission (EU Commission, 2024). 77% of monitoring points with Class 1 water quality fall under Risk Levels Insignificant and Low. 70% of monitoring points with Class 2 water quality fall under Risk Levels Low and Medium. 100% of monitoring points with Class 3 water quality fall under Risk Levels Medium and High. 60% of monitoring points with Class 4 water quality fall under Risk Levels Medium and High. The number of monitoring stations having Class 3 (2 stations) and 4 (5 stations) water quality are low and needs to be increased for better evaluation but there are representative number of stations for evaluation of monitoring stations having Class 1 (22 stations) and 2 (10 stations) water quality which show consistency with the risk analysis results.

Figure 1. Comparison of risk analysis of micro-watersheds and groundwater quality results for Gediz Basin

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support through Determination of Nitrate Vulnerable Zones and Preparation of Nitrate Action Plans Project (NITRATE) and EU Horizon Europe Project SMART4ENV under the agreement 101079251. The research leading to these results has received funding from the NITRATE Project supported by the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry.

REFERENCES

- Aydoner, C., 2024. Development and application of a GIS tool in the design of surface water quality monitoring networks: A micro-watershed-based approach. *Environmental Monitoring Assessment*, 196:985.
- Baalousha, H., 2010. Assessment of a groundwater quality monitoring network using vulnerability mapping and geostatistics: A case study from Heretaunga Plains, New Zealand. *Agricultural Water Management*, 97 (2), 240-246.
- De Maio, M., Fiorucci A., and Offi, M. 2007. Risk of groundwater contamination from nitrates in the Po basin (Italy). *Water Supply*, 7 (3), 83-92.

EU Commission, 2024. Status and trends of aquatic environment and agricultural practice-Guidelines for reporting under Article 10, ver 3.